

TERMINOLOGY DYNAMICS: UNVEILING THE ESSENCE, PRECISION, AND NATIONAL IDENTITY IN SPECIALIZED LANGUAGE

Aliyev Salman

*Lecturer of the Department of Russian and Oriental Languages,
Nakhchivan State University
ORCID: 0009-0008-5145-9491*

Guliyeva Lyudmila

*Lecturer of the Department of Russian and Oriental Languages,
Nakhchivan State University*

Abstract

This scholarly exploration delves into the intricate relationships among objects, concepts, terms, and definitions, employing Sounuuti's prism as a conceptual framework. Emphasizing the significance of mono-referentiality in scientific terminology, the article elucidates the defining characteristics of terms, underscoring their pivotal role in language evolution, cultural preservation, and national identity. The discussion culminates in a nuanced understanding of terminology dynamics in scientific, cultural, and technological domains.

Keywords: Term, Terminology, Object, Concept, Definition.

1. Interconnections among Object, Concept, Term, and Definition

Terms function as linguistic counterparts to concepts within specialized domains, embodying precise and well-defined meanings. An essential aspect in dis-

cussing terms lies in elucidating the intricate relationships between object, concept, and definition. In the realm of terminology research, a foundational step involves scrutinizing the conceptual landscape, its composition, and the interplay among concepts.

Pic.1 Sounuuti's prism

Figure illustrates the prism of object-concept-term-definition relationships. Contemplating the diagram reveals the interconnectedness of object, concept, definition, and term. The concrete entity at the prism's base is mentally abstracted, and subsequently, language (terms) becomes the conduit for expressing the conceptualized forms of tangible entities. Thus, when an individual perceives an object, they formulate a concept in their mind, necessitating the use of a term for articulating that conceptualization in communication. Nevertheless, in communicative scenarios where terms lack sufficient explication, individuals elucidate the terms through the application of definitions [6, p.13].

2. What is an Object?

In the explanatory dictionary of the Azerbaijani language, the definition of an object is provided as follows: "An external world existing independently of us and beyond our consciousness, a material entity" [1, p.510]. Anything existing in the external world that encompasses us is considered an object. Objects can be

both concrete (e.g., tree, book, water, car) and abstract (e.g., process, society, hygiene).

3. What is a Concept?

As observed in the aforementioned Sounuuti prism, a concept entails the abstract embodiment of objects in the mind. When we encounter an object, our brain formulates one or several specific characteristics related to that object, and these characteristics are objective features. The amalgamation of objective features shapes the concept. For instance, when we mention "fireworks" or "Nakhchivan Square," only a singular concept is formed in our minds, which is considered a specific concept. However, terms like street or square can evoke multiple concepts in our minds, termed general concepts. When expressed linguistically, a concept is referred to as a term in logic [4, p. 16]. Consequently, terms and concepts are closely intertwined, and the field of terminology explores concepts when naming scientific objects. H. Felber emphasizes that terminological activities should be based on concepts rather than terms [2, p.155-156].

There are various definitions related to concepts. Drawing attention to the definition provided by the International Organization for Standardization (ISO):

"A concept is generally a single cognitive unit expressed through a term, consisting of letters or any other symbols. Concepts are not mental representations of events or objects. Broadly speaking, they are mental representations of qualities (expressed with adjectives and nouns), actions (expressed with verbs and nouns), and spatial, positional, and relational aspects (expressed with adjectives, habits, bindings, or nouns)" [3, p. 3].

4. What Constitutes a Definition?

In Sounuuti's prism, following the object and concept, if the meaning of the ensuing term is unknown, a requisite step is to seek the definition of that term. This can be elucidated as follows: during the process of translation, individuals such as translators, students embarking on new disciplines, and those engaged in specialized scientific and technical literature, when confronted with an unfamiliar term, necessitate a definition for comprehension. The concept of definition is deeply rooted in various scientific disciplines, with Aristotle himself employing the phrase "the study of essence" in its explication. This concept has been extensively explored and utilized since the era of Aristotle. In the realm of logic, definition is the endeavor to articulate the essence and significance of a concept (term). This endeavor distinctly delineates the position of the concept and effectively distinguishes it from others [4, p.36; 5, p.103-104].

5. Unraveling the Notion of a Term

The lexicon of a language can be categorized into several groups, encompassing common operative words, idioms, and terms. Terms, distinguishable by their composition of one or more words or symbols, have been subject to varied definitions by numerous terminology researchers. The explanatory dictionary of the Azerbaijani language defines a term as follows: "A word (or combination of words) that precisely encapsulates the concept within a specific field of specialization such as science, technology, or art; a term" [1, p. 278].

Terms are inherently linked to specific domains of science or activities, facilitating effective communication among specialists. Notably, terms exhibit a propensity for singular meanings, a characteristic essential for precision [7, p. 192].

Beyond their function as a means of communication among specialists, terms serve as conduits for communication between specialists and non-specialists. In our contemporary society, a prevalent scenario arises from the heightened level of education, leading many individuals to employ terms outside their specialized domains. Possessing objective characteristics inherent to fields of science, professions, arts, or the economy, terms boast clearly defined meanings tailored for specific applications, impervious to arbitrary alterations. The precision and definitiveness of a term's meaning surpass that of ordinary words. Consequently, the meticulous crafting and establishment of interconnected meanings among terms within the same structures are imperative [7, p. 57].

When articulating a concept, it is imperative to employ a singular term from among several available options. Specifically, the relationships between terms within the same scientific domain ought to be unambiguous, adhering to a principle of mono-referentiality, wherein a single meaning corresponds to a single name [2, p.183].

In the broader discussion of terms, addressing two pivotal questions becomes paramount: 1) What defines a term? 2) How do terms distinguish themselves from other lexical entities? For a word to function as a term, certain attributes must be present, and those lacking these characteristics cannot be deemed terms. The quest for a comprehensive understanding of the term necessitates a focus on norms demarcating their definitive boundaries:

1. Singular and unequivocal meanings that preclude interpretation.
2. Immunity to contextual variations, distinct from common words, proverbs, or idioms.
3. Unambiguous meanings sourced from scientific literature.
4. Precision in expressing the intricate facets of scientific subjects.
5. Field specificity, with terms tailored to their respective domains.
6. Originating not from colloquial language but occasionally transitioning from vernacular to scientific usage.

The evolution of language within scientific, cultural, and technological spheres hinges on the richness of its terminological repertoire. Inadequate terminological diversity compels language users to resort to foreign languages, fostering linguistic intrusion and compromising linguistic integrity. Consequently, the significance of terms extends beyond specialist communication, playing a pivotal role in preserving the national identity of a language.

Terms frequently manifest as single or dual-word constructs, occasionally extending to three or more words. In instances of lengthier terms, acronyms emerge through the condensation of initial letters or specific segments of the constituent words, exemplified by abbreviations such as NATO, USA, and UN [1, p. 30].

In conclusion, this study underscores the paramount importance of precision and mono-referentiality in scientific terminology. The elucidation of terms' distinct characteristics, including unambiguous meanings and field specificity, reveals their crucial role in shaping language dynamics. Acknowledging the broader impact on cultural preservation and national identity, this research advocates for meticulous terminological practices to foster linguistic integrity in specialized discourse and beyond.

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